

Workshop report

Exploring paths for reflective practice and collaboration on citizen science and frugal innovation in Latin America and the Netherlands

Organized as part of the Prince Claus Chair in Equity Development (2023-2025)

at the International Institute of Social Studies, The Hague

April 3 and 4, 2025

1. Introduction

This report summarizes the workshop on citizen technoscience and frugal innovation in the context of environmental degradation that took place on April 3 and 4, 2025 at the International Institute of Social Studies (ISS) in The Hague, the Netherlands.

The workshop brought together researchers and practitioners working in the fields of citizen science and technology, frugal and grassroots innovation and participatory environmental governance in Latin America and the Netherlands. The workshop was organized by Prince Claus Chair holder Sebastián Ureta and ISS postdoctoral researcher Mandy Geise, as part of the Prince Claus Chair in Equity and Development's project on *Technology and Citizen Technoscience in the Context of Environmental Degradation*. In this project, Sebastián and Mandy explore how citizen science and technologies are used to measure, monitor and address different environmental phenomena such as soil and water pollution, water shortages and wildfires, and how such technologies might be (made to become more) participatory and reproduced to contribute to social and ecological transformation. Citizen science and frugal innovation seem to share many of the same goals and intentions and could strengthen community-centered responses to environmental degradation, but as two different fields of practice they might rely on other methods, language and locus of actors and framing of activities, creating a distance.

To address this gap and bring researchers and practitioners across the fields together, the workshop sought to initiate reflections beyond conventional narratives surrounding citizen science and frugal innovation and explore how they can complement each other.

In different sessions and formats participants shared experiences, exchanged knowledge and reflected on possible pathways to boost the sustainable use of accessible technologies by citizens. Participants discussed the potential and challenges for citizen science and frugal innovation to support communities, practitioners, researchers and policymakers in addressing environmental challenges through accessible and inclusive technologies. The workshop highlighted mutual learning and collective strategies to strengthen the sustainable use of technologies while being attentive to the multiple ways in which they might generate impact. This report summarizes the event, provides insights from the presented work and discussions, and identifies themes and initial steps for further discussion and collaboration. The conversations are grouped in three main themes – [interconnections](#), [impact](#) and [meaningful collaboration](#) – each containing insights regarding the challenges and possibilities for reflective practice, collaboration and supportive infrastructure within these categories described per subtheme. The workshop’s key takeaways are summarized in [a table on page 19](#).

2. Sharing insights from citizen science and frugal innovation experiences (Day 1)

Opening the event, Rosalba Icaza Garza, Deputy Rector of Research Affairs and Professor of Global Politics, Feminisms and Decoloniality at ISS, reflected on the role, potential and impact of citizen science and technologies in relation to the state of science and the social, political and environmental moment. PCC holder Sebastián Ureta provided an introduction to the concept of [citizen technoscience](#), in which simple, low-cost and accessible technologies provide citizens ways of measuring and addressing local manifestations of socioenvironmental issues, highlighting its potential for environmental and social transformation, particularly in Latin America. PCC postdoctoral researcher Mandy Geise shared insights and reflections drawn from the Prince Claus Chair research on the use, impact, and role of technologies in the three citizen science initiatives included as case studies.

The coordinators of those three citizen science initiatives in Mexico, Costa Rica and Chile then talked about their work. Arturo Hernández Velasco (Civil Association Comunidad y Biodiversidad) discussed several of the citizen science projects he has been involved in on the monitoring of water quality and fish populations by fishing communities in Mexico, including the app [PescaData](#), which small-scale fisheries can use to track their catches. María José Molina (AstraCodex) spoke about the initiative of [Rally Femenino](#), which trains women in the use of geospatial technologies, including in the development of their own prototypes, for example to use in agriculture and water and fire management. Sebastián Ureta, who coordinated the project [Nuestros Suelos](#), reflected on that initiative's process of developing and testing of a low-cost and easy to use kit, manual, and participative community workshops to assess soil pollution in areas with long histories of pollution and mining in Chile. The presentations illustrated the great diversity in shapes and approaches of citizen science projects as well as the different effects on communities and the socioecological context and how these were considered in the initiatives.

In the following discussion, the presenters and audience talked about the impact of citizen science and what interests and uses technologies and the data they create can serve in knowing and addressing environmental issues. The conversation highlighted how the value and function of citizen science and technology are deeply shaped by political and social contexts – and questioned whether new technologies and data are always necessary or beneficial. They might also create additional burdens or risks for citizens, practitioners, and researchers.

A key tension discussed was the gap between small-scale initiatives and broader systemic change, including the challenge of translating citizen science and frugal innovation into policy and institutional frameworks. The discussion also addressed the difficulty of embedding these practices in long-term strategies and the importance of creating stronger linkages between different localized efforts to have direct local impact as well as with larger social, scientific, political and/or environmental movements.

The first day concluded with a panel of practitioners and researchers active in citizen science and frugal innovation networks in Latin America and the Netherlands, who shared their practical experiences with citizen science and frugal innovation and the organizing of collaboration, knowledge exchange and infrastructural support through networks, platforms and centers. They introduced their experiences in these centers and networks before moving on to the panel discussion: Peter Knorringa introduced the [International Centre for Frugal Innovation](#) (ICFI), which explores frugal innovation and its economic, social and environmental impacts through multidisciplinary approaches across the world. Sarita Albagli presented some of the work done within [Cívís](#), the citizen science platform at the Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology. Allan Báez Morales discussed his work connecting engineers, designers, students and communities through the Santa Clara University [Frugal Innovation Hub](#) and the Latin American Network for Frugal Innovation (RELIF). Maria Alejandra Pineda spoke about citizen science projects on campus at the Politécnico Gran Colombia and frugal innovation partnerships with [RELIF](#). Karen Soacha Godoy spoke of efforts to build up citizen science infrastructure through her work at the Institut de Ciències del Mar and the Latin American Network for Participatory Science ([RICAP](#)).

In the panel discussion, panelists and audience deliberated on the needs, challenges and possibilities to move citizen science and frugal innovation initiatives from short-term innovation toward lasting social and environmental change and how networks and platforms could support this. This conversation would continue the next day in the small work group discussions.

3. Central themes, challenges and possibilities for impactful collaboration in citizen science and frugal innovation (Day 2)

On the second day, participants reflected on three core topics in small groups:

1. Interconnections between citizen science and frugal innovation
2. The meaning of impact and how to understand and demonstrate it
3. Building meaningful collaborations

Bringing experiences and perspectives from working on a wide range of projects and networks in different settings, participants talked about challenges for citizen science and frugal innovation initiatives to achieve short and long-term impacts. They discussed ways in which citizen science and frugal innovation efforts might be connected, and how to partner up between the fields as well as in partnerships with community members and other stakeholders. They also suggested some concrete ways in which barriers could be overcome and some first next steps they could be pursuing, mixing local strategies with international collaborative efforts in research, dissemination of knowledge, and institutional support.

The discussions are summarized by main themes and take-away insights distilled below. They point to some of the challenges they currently face and especially how citizen science and frugal

innovation could have a more sustained impact through collaborating across the fields and with different stakeholders.

3.1 Interconnections

One set of discussions centered on interconnections between citizen science and frugal innovation. Participants talked about possible ways in which researchers and practitioners of citizen science and frugal innovation can find connections and link practices, perspectives, data and infrastructure. These might be starting points for collaboration.

The group explored how different fields of practice – citizen science, participatory science, grassroots technology, frugal innovation, maker and hacker movements – can interconnect to strengthen impact and lessen fragmentation, while also recognizing risks of co-optation, competition and depoliticization. Participants agreed that collaboration across these fields can create greater impact by combining strengths: citizen science contributes local knowledge, data and community engagement, while frugal innovation offers methods for developing affordable, user-friendly and context-sensitive technologies. Key challenges include different approaches, siloed initiatives, difficulty maintaining platforms and overreliance on costly contractors for technology development.

Intermediary organizations and universities could help bridge gaps by fostering awareness, documentation of grassroots innovations, and low-cost, perhaps student-led, prototyping. Participants from both the citizen science and frugal innovation fields emphasized the importance of responsible, transparent and participatory development which directly engages stakeholders.

Defining and connecting citizen science and frugal innovation

Citizen science and frugal innovation share similarities and differences, but both offer communities tools, knowledge and skills that allow them to do use technology and generate knowledge (e.g. data) on their own. Participants discussed the existing debates about definitions of frugal innovation and citizen science, particularly in Asia and Latin America. In Latin America there is a long history of social movements using technologies and innovation and terms such as “grassroots”, “social citizen innovation” and “social technologies” are more commonly used. One of the participants voiced worries that introducing the terminology but also some of the practices of frugal innovation, with start-ups and private companies, might invisibilize or bring cooptation of social and communal processes that have already been happening for many years. One of the frugal innovation researchers responded that cooptation could be a risk with developing new technologies, but its guiding values of affordability, accessibility and embeddedness in the local context that should protect it from being hijacked by market logic. Nonetheless, both with frugal innovation and citizen science collaborations it is necessary to define motivations, objectives and expectations. And participants flag that is important to keep histories of certain practices and movements in mind when seeking collaborations in the region as it might not be clear what frugal innovation or citizen science initiatives might seek to do.

Bringing complementary fields together

Participants saw the value of interconnection as building broader networks and spaces of exchange between diverse fields of practice such as citizen science, frugal innovation and grassroots technologies, without creating a “super institution.” They saw benefits in sharing lessons, knowledge, and practices across fields through common platforms, as frugal innovation and citizen science share a focus on social impact, but often operate in silos. Citizen science could gain from frugal innovation’s context-sensitive, resource-aware design methods. Frugal innovation could benefit from citizen science’s community knowledge, data, and content, which is essential for making technology meaningful and usable.

Common spaces for exchange and collaboration can be bridges not only between the different fields of practice but also between different stakeholders. As initiatives evolve, the stages they go through (idea, prototype, diffusion) could also influence what connections, tools, knowledge and actions are needed and different expertise could be applied at the appropriate times with the help of a platform.

Both fields of practice stress participatory development and the importance of grounding technology in lived realities. However, citizen science and frugal innovation traditionally view knowledge and expertise differently, which can complicate collaboration. They might also remain separated because of terminology and identity. Participants especially saw how exchange on tools and methods could work out well, and accommodating for the differences in discipline, tradition and epistemology would also be possible but require more guided processes. It will also be beneficial to capture project outcomes and lessons in formats that are easy to share and adapt across contexts. Participants also stressed that knowledge politics and the sociopolitical embeddedness of initiatives are generally different. While, in their experience, citizen science tends to be more explicitly political (e.g. water scarcity framed as an environmental justice issue or using rights and anti-privatization discourses), frugal innovation often avoids politics and focuses on technical solutions, which may limit transformative potential. Interconnective approaches would need deliberation on whether and how to politicize innovation projects. Participants suggested that how to best approach this was to be further explored.

Making knowledge visible: mapping, learning and knowledge sharing

Many initiatives exist but often remain unseen, unknown and/or isolated. This complicates learning and knowledge sharing and makes it hard to build momentum for broader social change. Participants cited examples of indigenous communities receiving funding from multiple organizations, leading to overlapping but disconnected projects. Others pointed to the wealth of grassroots innovations, for example of farmers adapting to climate change, which is mostly undocumented (though there are also examples of inventories or databases that have mapped this, such as in Chile). Such invisibility and fragmentation means that (local) knowledge doesn’t figure on the map and can neither inform other initiatives through travelling “upwards” to scientists, organizations, governments, etc.) nor by traveling horizontally and reaching neighbors and peers who might benefit. While not in all cases, peer-to-peer connections are often lacking and relationships are there between communities, scientists and (international) organizations, instead of sideways to neighbors. Participants agreed it is a task for researchers and practitioners across

citizen science and frugal innovation to improve exchange between citizens and communities and to facilitate the use and circulations of local(ly created) knowledge. Participants suggested mapping, recognizing and supporting citizen- and community-based action through digital platforms and local consortiums, to document and circulate local solutions as well as matching needs with expertise (e.g. citizen scientists with local fab labs). Other interconnection and exchange methods could be living labs, local workshops, or “solution finder” initiatives where communities define needs and co-develop solutions with technical partners. These can be preferred over hackathons, which can spark collaboration but are often elitist, short-term and disconnected from real community needs.

The participants were aware that digital platforms aiming to connect groups often fail due to siloed mindsets, lack of trust or limited stakeholder engagement. A mapping exercise might be an accessible way to start and could be used to get interested parties on board. Support from already existing organizations might also help with sustainability. They suggested that organizations like the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) can serve as connectors by raising awareness and mapping existing initiatives.

Cooptation, depoliticization and freeing projects from external experts

Many citizen science initiatives struggle with the high costs of skilled IT labor, relying heavily on external contractors for application and platform development, which creates high expenses that might otherwise have been spent on other parts of the process and on top often lacks contextual sensitivity. Universities and students could help offer an alternative, offering low-cost prototyping and human-centered design approaches. This is a strategy used in frugal innovation, where for example engineering and design students develop products for and with local communities in a way that emphasizes hyperlocal, affordable and user-friendly design. There are concerns that frugal innovation or grassroots initiatives can be absorbed by a “start-up” or consultancy logic, shifting focus from collective change to market products. Frugal innovation and citizen science initiatives

alike face the risk that their technology or data becomes a tool for businesses or governments to sustain exploitative systems instead of transforming them. Companies may fund initiatives as a way to “keep communities busy” without real accountability. As one of the participants mentioned, citizen science projects sometimes reduce activism to endless data collection, diverting energy away from direct political action (e.g., protests, claims for remediation). One of the participants pointed to the importance of “data readiness”, recognizing when enough data has been collected and it’s time to act or move on. There are also issues of data ownership (e.g. farmers’ GPS mapping) highlighting risks of corporate control over community-generated data.

Participants agreed that some of this can be countered by leveraging technology responsibly: through transparent co-design with communities and avoiding “black box” algorithms. And it is important to be aware of how data and technologies support adaptation vs. transformation, as well as when knowledge is created for and used by institutions and/or for communities. Some innovations help communities adapt but do not challenge structural inequalities. Participants agree that there is a need for both technologies that help adapt in the short term and those that aim for transformation. But in the end, we should seek to support communities in empowerment and not recreate dependency on external experts. Autonomy as well as support and recognition of local knowledge and skills are central to sustaining initiatives and ensuring relevance.

Toward practical next steps

Participants suggested the following ideas to advance interconnections between citizen science and frugal innovation:

- Documenting frugal/grassroots innovations and merging them into citizen science platforms.
- Testing small joint projects that merge frugal innovation methods with citizen science goals.
- Focusing on local stakeholders and real impacts to sustain engagement.
- Create spaces for exchange between researchers, practitioners and communities in citizen science and those in frugal innovation, for example webinars, workshops and living labs.

3.2 Impact

Another set of discussions revolved around the concept of impact, its various dimensions, and how to measure it. The participants discussed different ways to think about impact, including social, ecological, scientific and political impact, replicability and scalability, sustainability, and community-centered design. They also discussed the challenges of measuring impact, particularly in the context of long-term projects and initiatives.

Citizen science and frugal innovation projects often get stuck or fade out after their initial phases because of vanishing funding, lack of institutional support, discontinuity of staff and technical equipment, or regulatory barriers. While short-term projects can help to bring about immediate results, participants envisioned these as most helpful as part of long-term initiatives that consider

the structural aspects and different dimensions of impact across time. Participants stressed that for citizen science and frugal innovation projects to survive and thrive beyond their initial stages, sustainability and adaptability are as important as innovation. Greater interest and investment in follow-up requires shifts across research, implementing, funding and supporting institutions to ensure long-term support, staff and technical equipment, regulatory openings and enthusiasm.

How to capture impact: usage, transformation, sustainability and scalability

In the discussions two ways of considering impact emerged, one that centers the technology and another that centers social change or transformation. Some participants from the frugal innovation field mentioned impact can be assessed by the design, usability, uptake, sustainability and circulation (including scalability and replicability) of a technology. Other participants brought up the effects a technology and/or data and knowledge created might have on behavior, social structures, ecologies, policies and scientific knowledge. These aspects do not operate independently of one another but are connected with – and often directly dependent on – one another. Sustainability and scalability are meaningful only when adapted to local needs and conditions, and design must support community adoption for impact to be realized and sustained. However, they do have different approaches to assessing impact.

When thinking of the design and circulation of the product, certain features were mentioned as integral to defining and facilitating impact. Technology can help with understanding impact on a direct/user level, especially when developed through a frugal innovation mindset. Tracking the usage of the developed or newly adapted technologies, for example when developing a mobile phone application, will make it possible to tell how many people used the application, the functions they interacted with, how much and what kind of data they put in, etc. Participants emphasized the importance of ethical tracking in such cases and the importance of critically questioning the reliance on devices or applications that might be embedded in capitalist models or unethical practices. But

tracking usage is an immediate report that can support impact assessment and scalability and could also be provided to funders.

Scalability is seen as depending on financial sustainability; some of the participants stated that for scaling up a technology there will almost always have to be some sort of revenue creation be tied with it. Social (local) enterprises could be a logical actor in these cases, they might offer sustained approaches while having business models that center communities and impact. Nonetheless, here too, there is a struggle with being self-sustaining if not wanting to charge citizen users.

Finally, as was stressed, while thinking about scalability is relevant if seeking to reach more people, one might not always want to extend reach in that way. In any case, a blanket approach to scalability or technology should be avoided.

Participants stressed that when seeking to extend technologies or innovations to other places, it is essential they are adapted or made adaptable to local needs and conditions. Community-centered design can help to ensure adoption and community ownership. Several participants emphasized the importance to have citizens involved from the early stages and ask about their needs. This helps with ownership and control over the innovation process, an aspect highlighted by the participants as important for empowering local communities. Involving users early on can help ensure that the technology is well designed for the context, easy for people to start and continue using it, and clearly offers them added value so that they interact with it and might show it to others.

When considering transformative impact, a participant said, “we look at what actually changes in people’s lives, which can happen in many different ways: behavioral impact, social impact, economic impact, policy impact”. Participants gave examples of where citizen science projects have brought this kind of impact, such as regarding air pollution, which has become a matter of policy concern, while twenty years ago air pollution was dismissed by policy makers. Participants noted that social, behavioral, economic and/or policy impact together with scaling up can lead to mainstreaming.

And one of the participants reminded us that the perhaps abstract terms “transformation” and “impact” become more tangible when we tackle them in small steps: “in order to have that transformative potential, that's a huge task so, so we need to be taking small steps and focus on how we as scientists and practitioners can connect better and to make sure that what we're doing is solid.”

Adaptive innovation and technology as a tool, not a solution

Participants with experience in citizen science and frugal innovation saw technologies as a means, not an end. Participants argued that:

- Technology should only be used if necessary
- Sometimes the use of existing technologies or non-technological or low-tech solutions is more effective
- Technological tools should enhance, not overshadow, the role of communities

The participants noted that technology can be both an enabler and a barrier to frugal innovations and citizen science projects, particularly in areas with limited access to resources and infrastructure. It all depends on the way and with what purpose the technology is introduced, designed and applied.

Participants agreed that technology is not the solution, but a tool to address an identified issue. And sometimes technology is not even part of the solution. One participant mentioned that in frugal innovation, among the first questions asked in a trajectory are whether technology is necessary to reach the objective and if new technology needs to be developed. After considering different kinds of approaches and solutions the conclusion might be that no (new) technology is needed as there is already something that will allow for good enough solutions. This exemplifies frugal innovation's basic principles to leveraging local resources and adaptation of existing technologies to "make things work" in the specific context. Adapting and recontextualizing existing innovations to suit local needs and conditions can help to bridge the gap between individual projects. Such adaptive innovation also allows us to look at scalability beyond how it often captured in business or economics terms, "repeating it and doing it bigger in the same way". Through adaptively and recontextualizing a technology or innovation, citizen science and frugal innovation initiatives can reach and involve more people in a way that is relevant and beneficial in each (new) setting. Scalability is understood then as a different, more adaptable concept.

Measuring impact

Impact can be slippery to measure, especially long-term change. Participants felt projects often focus more on process (collecting data, building tools) than on impact (social transformation, local empowerment). Currently, projects are generally not designed to identify their impact, and thus impact is often not measured or documented, leaving project leaders and participants without knowing where and what the impact was. Still, two strategies of building in ways of measuring and reflecting on impact were emphasized as useful:

- **Impact by design:** Building reflection on impact into every stage of a project, with attention to both positive and negative consequences. Mapping stakeholders and unintended outcomes early helps refine direction.
- **Roots and fruits:** Projects should aim to have and reflect on both long-term and short-term tangible outcomes.

An "impact by design" approach implies keeping track of impact throughout the process, something participants mentioned having struggled with in previous projects. Such an approach depends on putting in place mechanisms for a reflective process that allows for ongoing assessment (and adaptation) during a project, and gather data for various dimensions, including social, environmental, ethical, political, economic and institutional – and if appropriate, also epistemological and infrastructural – impact. A strategy of "impact by design" will have impact as a main driver of a project, and potential consequences of a project or initiative are considered from the outset and in every stage, with attention to both positive and negative effects. Measuring impact starts with thinking about who might be benefitting from a technology and in what ways. This can

include carrying out a mapping of stakeholders and (un)intended outcomes for each stakeholder, which can help clarify where the impact might be, what the impact might be, how it might unfold and how it can be measured and documented. A SWAT or Theory of Change could help here as well, also in communicating the project or technology to community stakeholders and funders.

Some impacts are only visible decades later, others can yield quicker results. Projects should aim to have, and assess, both long-term goals and short-term tangible outcomes. For example, in biodiversity monitoring, the impact of thousands of people collecting data may only be evident in the long term, possibly identifying new species or extinctions. Continuous data gathering is needed in order to identify such developments, but its effects might take years or even decades to manifest. But while nurturing foundational data is essential, we must also pursue quicker outcomes, akin to planting and seeing growth within months. As one participant stated, “we need to work on the roots, keep collecting and working with the data even if it is going to take time to see what it's going to produce. But we also need to think in the fruits and flowers, like when you plant something and in six months it's giving you something and you see change. But the roots are there to support it all.” Similarly, one can think of women capacitated in using irrigation data and technology (short-term), which might lead to overall better water management, food production and food safety (mid-term), and more efficient use of soil, plot surface, water and time allowing for other activities, possibly affecting health, economic and social position and water shortages (long-term). This underscores balancing long-term effects (in this case, for knowledge accumulation) with addressing current social and environmental challenges. And it is not only about how do to reach a certain level of impact but also about how to sustain it.

It is also important to convey to funders that both immediate and future (and sustained) impacts are necessary for meaningful progress. Funding is now often limited to short-term projects. Participants agreed that funding for longer periods and a focus on structural instead of project-based support could facilitate both making impact and reporting on it. Additionally, rather than criteria for “participation” and “public engagement”, which often apply very narrow standards of civic participation, funders like the European Union might want to fund on the basis of transformative potential instead. This would also strengthen citizen science as a democratic right to participate in knowledge production, and structural transformation. The discussion on funders also brought up the question of language to use to communicate impact, and by whose and which standards we should be thinking about impact.

Communicating impact

The discussion highlighted the need to speak the language of different audiences and to effectively communicate impact to different stakeholders, including funders, policymakers and community members. The participants emphasized the importance of using language and narratives that resonate with these audiences, while also being mindful of the ethical implications of their work. They shared experiences with funders and policy makers seeking to hear catchy language, which can feel as using empty buzzwords and “mimicking someone else’s vocabulary”. However, they do confess to replicating that language to convey to funders and policy makers that they are being taken seriously and to show the close alignment of the project proposal or results with their interests. Or the language can be business-like or engineering-oriented as terms from engineering and business tend to resonate with more people because of the current cultural moment, including with people that might be in a position to make decisions about financing, (infra)structural support and policies. It can be easy to get drawn in by writing proposals or results communications with these people in mind and not necessarily the involved citizens. So, participants argued, it is important to strike a balance between using language that attracts different research, practice and funding partners and keeps in mind the different kinds of impact and needs of communities. And, as one of the participants pointed out, as researchers and practitioners we have a role in generating changes in the way impact is talked about and perceived. We can offer resistances and point out potential transformations, issues of power and social justice to funders and policymakers, even if (mostly) talking to them in a way that speaks to them.

Knowledge sharing

Beyond language, participants highlighted the challenges of sharing knowledge and codifying data in a way that makes it reusable and accessible to others, both with those involved in a project and those outside of it. This can involve sharing data collected, manuals or toolkits, analyses, webinars with people we have worked with in a project, but also with people working elsewhere. Citizen science and frugal innovation projects are shaped by a wide range of approaches and have different forms of and approaches to data. In these projects knowledge is created and circulates in different ways, and for it to be made reusable and accessible requires crystallizing the knowledge so it can be shared across different publics. This is also essential for replication and broader community use. Such sharing relies on appropriate infrastructure and platforms for sharing data, insights and other

knowledge in a way that can help involved communities, researchers, practitioners, developers and designers, civil society and government actors. There are several initiatives for developing infrastructure and platforms to share and circulate underway, such as [RIECS](#). RIECS aims to be a research infrastructure that fosters ongoing dialogue among citizens, practitioners, researchers, funders and policymakers; offers harmonized training and capacity-building; and robust quality assurance frameworks that will ensure that data generated by citizen science meet the standards needed for scientific and policy use. But also in the networks, such as Cívís, RELIF, RICAPS and ECSA, efforts are often already disseminated, for example through webinars.

Regarding communication within projects, participants agreed that as researchers and practitioners we need to continuously ask how we can ensure that the information collected on the ground can be returned to communities in a way that they can understand and use for good. This demands an attentiveness to the needs of the community, and to critical issues of power, social relations, justice and local knowledge. Without attention to these critical issues, existing inequalities may be replicated and further embedded by citizen science or frugal innovation projects. Participants called for socially and culturally aware, place-based innovation and science practices, including in communication and knowledge sharing. Peer-to-peer communication can also be important in knowledge sharing and involving possible new citizen scientists, too. It can improve trust, rapport and relevance. For example, for the Rally Femenino training events, women farmers persuaded peers to join more effectively than outsiders, underscoring the importance of peer-to-peer trust and relatability. As work with fishing communities in Mexico has shown, communities might see *how* a technology or project could work for them if they see how it has worked for neighboring communities.

Toward next steps

Ultimately, participants stressed the need for ongoing dialogue, critical reflection and flexible frameworks to guide meaningful, inclusive, and lasting impact based on collaboration between stakeholders, including researchers, practitioners and community members. Suggestions for next steps to tackle some of the challenges of measuring the impact of frugal innovations and citizen science projects, as well as the difficulties of scaling up successful initiatives were:

- Explore impact by design approaches
- Roots and fruits
- Document community-centered approach and impact
- Develop (or agree on existing) shared guidelines or principles on how to map communicate with community members and other involved stakeholders

3.3 Collaboration

The third set of discussions revolved around collaboration in the context of citizen science and frugal innovation. The discussion touched upon various forms, challenges and opportunities of collaboration. The experiences participants discussed highlighted the great diversity in citizen science and frugal innovation initiatives and the social, political, economic circumstances in which initiatives take place. These can greatly affect what collaboration looks like (and what the different

involved partners may want it to look like). Institutional aspects can also affect with whom, how and when we collaborate.

Participants proposed developing a typology of collaboration with the goal of identifying which types of collaboration might work well for a specific citizen science or frugal innovation project, with the caveat that its applicability still depends on the specific goals and context of the project.

Defining (meaningful) collaboration

Participants emphasized that collaboration is important but not a given and cannot be approached as uniform and rigid. Collaboration can take multiple forms and the kind of collaborating actors can also be very different, with possible collaborations between scientists, lay or expert citizens, product developers, civil society organizations, local or national government, advocacy groups, and others. The moment and length of collaboration may also differ. Some participants argued that collaboration with multiple kinds of actors is inherent to the practices of citizen science and frugal innovation, while others suggested that it may not always be necessary or desirable. Citizen science also does not necessarily require the participation of both citizens and scientists; the example of citizens in Japan working together to measure radioactive areas was cited as an instance of collaboration that did not involve scientists. As this example showed, citizens can play a crucial role in collaboration, which does not necessarily involve institutional mediation but can be on a peer-to-peer basis, facilitated by access to open source soft- and hardware as well as easily accessible data. This is one kind of a more horizontal approach in which citizens are not merely data providers but active co-creators.

A co-creative approach to collaboration is a valuable way of working together that raises chances of empowering citizens, not only enabling them to work with data and technologies but also providing input and steering the citizen science or frugal innovation process. Some participants emphasized

that involvement throughout all phases of the project is likely to increase ownership of the process and raises chances for targeted impact. However, as some of the participants argued, while co-creation can be fitting in many projects, in others it might be more appropriate to have citizen participants in more of a user, trainee or consultation role. So it is important to see what is most fitting and feasible in the context.

Funding and institutional constraints

The main challenges participants mentioned were funding and institutional support, power imbalances, lack of defined roles and aims, and institutional and knowledge hierarchies.

Power imbalances, mistrust, and unclear roles often prevent meaningful partnerships. Which is why it is so important to establish a clear purpose, expectations and goals, as well as recognizing limitations, the participants emphasized. There should be a definition of, and agreement on, aims and objectives, both those that overlap and those that might be relevant to an individual collaborating partner. This foundation will be solidified by agreeing on what can be attained and how it will be reached by defining steps and tasks for partners. While realities and practices may differ, clearly setting goals and tasks will help keep things in check. This might also help prevent practices with partners appropriating the process, data or technology.

Funding regulations contribute to power imbalances. One way in which they do so is through eligibility requirements, which often exclude grassroots initiatives from being eligible for funding. This makes civil society initiatives dependent on partnerships universities and research institutes for applying for funding and coordinating the project when granted. Academic and other research institutes are regarded as bastions of superior knowledge and function as gatekeepers. Participants would like to see more possibilities for obtaining funding with civil society organizations or other grassroots initiatives as fully recognized leaders or partners. This could give a boost to bottom-up approaches where communities lead, with external actors providing support rather than imposing solutions.

Participants from Latin America also noted that there is a lack of trust between organizations and competition for recognition and “ownership” of projects or ideas. Universities and civil society organizations are struggling with collaboration due to this competitive landscape, which has led to duplication of initiatives within the same institution without collaboration.

Several participants noted that collaboration and impact can furthermore be hindered by the fact that funding tends to be project-based and agencies often require projects to be completed within a limited timeframe, which can restrict the development of long-term relationships and infrastructure. Funding is also regularly tied to very specific requirements and earmarked for targeted actions and outcomes, rather than efforts towards building up and maintaining collaboration. Neither infrastructure nor collaboration are included in the majority of project calls, creating a large need. As one participant said, “the funding needs to be for relationships and collaborations and not project-based, the collaboration itself needs to be funded.” This could be something similar to EU COST funding which funds relationship-building and working together.

Changing partners and funding landscapes

Researchers and practitioners face a decline in traditional funding sources, and this is especially so for those based in Latin America relying on funding from the US, but also in Europe the landscape is changing. In seeking alternative models, participants suggested alternative funding sources and institutional frameworks to foster collaboration between Latin American and European groups. Collaborations with new partners can also bring tensions in collaboration practices, expectations and requirements that might come with different cultures and institutions. For example, one participant notes that in Latin America, there is a culture of solving problems with the resources available, whereas European partners or funders may emphasize strict protocols and procedures. The current moment is also an opportunity for more South-South cooperation, including between Latin American and African countries. Participants expressed interest in having more scientific partners in the Global South to foster exchange of experiences, methods and technologies in settings that might be characterized by similar situations where frugal innovation or citizen science is carried out.

Data ownership and afterlife of data

Concerns over data ownership, extraction and sovereignty can be complicated in collaboration, especially international collaboration. Different national legislations regarding data can create barriers to sharing and cooperation. At the same time, ensuring communities have control over data that concerns them is important. The afterlife of data raises ethical questions about who benefits from the data, and how data are secured. Participants noted that the collection and use of data can have significant implications for citizens, researchers and practitioners, particularly in contexts where there might be inequality, repression and other forms of violence. As researchers, practitioners and developers we need to take care of the citizen participants, and safeguard the security and usability of the data or technology. The storage, access and use of the data needs to be

agreed upon clearly and align with guidelines for safe (and anonymous) data storage. And we need to consider what happens with the technology and data after a project might be over.

Towards next steps

Participants acknowledged the need for further shared exploration and debate on what meaningful collaboration could look like in (their) different settings, and the importance of considering the various forms and challenges of collaboration in different contexts. Ultimately, collaboration requires careful negotiation of values, practices, and power relations, alongside recognition of the creativity and resilience communities already bring to the table.

Suggestions included exploring:

- whether a typology of collaboration can help identify best practices without oversimplifying diverse contexts
- seek out or propose funding structures that better support long-term, trust-based collaboration

4. Concluding the workshop and continuing the conversation

The discussions concluded with a collectively summarizing and reflecting session on the key takeaways regarding interconnection, collaboration and impact. Reflecting on the promises and pitfalls of interconnecting citizen science and frugal innovation, participants reiterated that opportunities lie in combining community knowledge with practical innovation, but barriers include depoliticization through endless data collection, and the risk of co-optation by institutions or markets. Participants asserted the importance of considering impact from multiple perspectives, the need for effective communication and measurement, and the value of "impact by design" in guiding project development. Collaboration offers opportunities for building bridges across regions, disciplines and actors, but faces persistent challenges related to funding, institutional barriers, mistrust, and power asymmetries. Participants emphasized the need to recognize political dimensions, and build trust-based, sustainable collaborations.

The key takeaways from the workshop are summarized in the following table:

Main Theme	Key Discussion Points	Highlighted Challenges
Interconnections between citizen science and frugal innovation	Citizen science contributes local knowledge, data and community engagement, while frugal innovation offers affordable, user-friendly and context-sensitive technologies	The risk of co-optation and depoliticization is significant, where initiatives might be absorbed by a "start-up" logic or divert activist energy into endless data collection
	The aim is to strengthen impact and reduce fragmentation by combining strengths from different fields	"Data readiness": knowing when enough data has been collected and it's time to act

	Responsible, transparent and participatory development involving stakeholders is crucial for both	The need for autonomy and recognition of local knowledge and skills for the sustainability of initiatives
	Knowledge politics and sociopolitical embeddedness: citizen science tends to be more explicitly political, while frugal innovation often focuses on technical solutions	Balancing technologies for short-term adaptation with those seeking long-term structural transformation
	The importance of making knowledge visible through mapping, digital platforms and workshops was stressed, preferring "solution finder" initiatives over hackathons	
The meaning of impact and how to understand and demonstrate it	Impact considered across social, ecological, scientific, political and economic dimensions, as well as replicability, scalability and sustainability	Projects often fade after initial phases due to vanishing funding, lack of institutional support, staff discontinuity, equipment shortages and regulatory barriers
	Immediate results are valuable, but structural and sustained impacts (policy change, community empowerment, knowledge accumulation) require long-term support	The need for long-term funding and structural support valuing transformative potential. Short-term funding cycles restrict sustainability; long-term impacts often invisible to funders and not adequately tracked
	Two approaches to impact: technology-centered or transformation-centered	Over-emphasizing tools over social transformation; blanket scalability approaches may ignore local context
	Community-centered design, involving citizens from early stages, is key for technology adoption and ownership	Focus on tools over social transformation; blanket scalability approaches ignoring local context risk being irrelevant, unused or imposed
	Technology is a tool, not a solution, and sometimes non- or low-tech solutions are more effective. Frugal innovation leverages local resources and adapting existing technologies	Dependency on devices embedded in capitalist or unethical models. Achieving financial sustainability to scale technologies, without charging citizen users
	Two proposed key strategies for measuring impact: "impact by design" and "roots and fruits" (seeking tangible short-term and long-term outcomes).	Measuring impact during and after projects, for different stakeholders. Projects often designed without built-in impact assessment; long-term impacts difficult to measure or only visible decades later

	Communicating impact by adapting language to different audiences without losing sight of local needs. Trust and relatability (e.g., peer communication) strengthen adoption and impact	Returning knowledge to communities in an understandable and useful way, paying attention to social justice, power and local knowledge to avoid replicating inequalities. Pressure to use buzzwords may overshadow needs
	Need for platforms to make data and insights reusable and accessible for knowledge sharing	Without proper frameworks, knowledge stays fragmented; risk of reproducing inequalities
Building meaningful collaborations	Collaboration is not uniform or guaranteed; it can take multiple forms and does not always require scientists' participation	Different goals, contexts and expectations make defining meaningful collaboration complex. Competition for recognition and duplication of efforts
	Co-creative approaches are valuable for empowering citizens as active participants, increasing ownership and impact	Recognizing and valuing the creativity and resilience that communities already bring to the table. Risk of tokenism or misalignment of roles
	The idea of more funding for relationships and collaborations, seeking models that support long-term trust-building	Project-based funding hinders long-term relationships; eligibility rules often exclude grassroots initiatives, academic institutes act as gatekeepers
	Power dynamics and the need to set clear purposes, goals, expectations, and roles in collaborations	Power imbalances, lack of clear roles and objectives, knowledge hierarchies and mistrust
	The funding landscape is changing, interest in opportunities for South-South cooperation	Cultural tensions in international collaboration, such as differences in problem-solving
	Ethical concerns about data ownership, extraction and sovereignty, especially in contexts of inequality or repression	Safeguarding data and technologies security and usability, and to consider the storage, access and afterlife of data, with clear and ethical agreements

The workshop discussions will inform ongoing conversations amongst participants and other key partners and support further collaboration between those working at the intersections of citizen science, frugal innovation and environmental degradation in Latin America and the Netherlands. We look forward to further work on this with the participants and others and invite the participants to reach out to us and one another for ongoing discussions and collaborations. Amongst some participants, new or revamped collaboration has been sparked and there is already some follow up work planned. We hope to further join forces in research, practice and in the strengthening or diversifying of networks and infrastructures that support community-centered science, technology and innovation.

5. Acknowledgments

We thank all participants for their contributions during and in preparation of the workshop. Their insights, reflections and critical questions made the discussions not only engaging but also sparked new inspirations and ways to collaborate with one another, other practitioners, community members and partners.

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6. List of participants

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